

COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT (CAI) PROPERTIES OF HAT STIFFENED CF/PEEK PANELS FABRICATED THROUGH A ROUTE WITHOUT AUTOCLAVE

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SUMMARY: Compression after impact (CAI) properties in composite structure levels were experimentally obtained and examined. A remarkable feature in the fabrication technology of the test piece panels was the fusion bonding process without autoclave. This route was pursued for possible low cost fabrication methodology of carbon fiber (CF)/thermoplastic composites exhibiting an excellent damage tolerance property. Used test specimens were stiffened panels with hat shaped stiffeners regarded as optimal for CF/thermoplastic, CF/PEEK being chosen here. Two kinds of panels in size were tested in compression loading after drop weight impact for creating delamination. The results are compared with the previous similar CAI tests for T-stiffened panels of CF/PEEK where the present results exhibit higher CAI values. A potential of this fusion bonding technology without autoclave is indicated. Numerical analysis for predicting initial buckling stress was also conducted with a favorable agreement with experiments.

KEYWORDS: experiments, impact, delamination, thermoplastic composites, fusion bonding, ultrasonic C-Scan, buckling, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

Damage tolerance properties of composites are considered to be important design criticals in their application to aircraft structures. Particularly, importance of compression after impact (CAI) values have been recognized in strength design of composite wing or fuselage in recent years. Therefore, NAL of JAPAN has been conducting a long term research project [1] for development of tough composite structures to aircraft component. A chosen material system in this project was CF/PEEK. After basic material properties including compression after impact (CAI) strengths for NASA type thick plates [2] were obtained, stiffened panels with four T-shaped stiffeners were tested [3,4] as structural level CAI evaluations. Based on such achievement, two model wing box structures of CF/PEEK were built and tested [1,5] in fatigue loading followed by residual static strength tests. The results of these boxes exhibited high delamination propagation resistance and excellent strength properties. In summary, a possibility of 35 % weight reduction by CF/PEEK from a baseline metal structure was verified [1] even in a conservative estimate.

However, one major disadvantage of CF/PEEK was also revealed through this work. Since it requires high temperature and pressure during fabrication procedure, its autoclave processing may lead to high cost because of expensive autoclave itself and tooling. This fact could be an obstacle for rapid spreading of CF/PEEK material into aerospace composite community. Based on such a background, a fabrication technique without an autoclave has been pursued by NAL and Fuji Heavy Industries Inc. (FHI) in JAPAN for realizing low cost thermoplastic composite structures. A possible solution might be non-traditional hot-pressing where an appropriate shape of stiffeners is also a key point of concern. The present paper describes recent results of this research program. A detailed description of fabrication process [6] will be minimized and the focus will be placed on presentation and discussion of experimental CAI properties. Numerical analysis of them with locally delaminated hat stiffeners at skin-stiffener interface was also conducted using a commercially available finite element code.

DESCRIPTION OF TEST SPECIMENS

As stated before, material employed was CF/PEEK (AS4/APC-2). Shape and dimensions of a smaller test panel stiffened by single hat are shown in Fig.1, which is considered to be a prototype of larger panels. The larger panel dimensions stiffened by three hats are shown in Fig.2. A hat shaped stiffener was chosen for its compatibility with secondary fusion bonding to a flat skin and anti-buckling properties. A key point of the fusion bonding technique without autoclave is a development of a mold-platen containing line heaters. At first, a technique with PEEK film was established and two smaller panels were fabricated with this route, designated as CPA03 and 04. A problem of non-uniform thickness distribution in skin-stiffener attachment flanges remained unsolved in this phase probably due to re-softening mentioned later. Next, several thermoplastic films with lower melting point than PEEK and methods for fusion promotion into CF/PEEK substrate structure were tried in their combinations. Some screening interlaminar toughness and strength tests were conducted and a combination of PEI and pre-fusion to a substrate was selected [6]. A benefit of this technique is that re-softening and deformation in the previously formed region can be minimized during fusion bonding. One larger panel designated as CPB02 was fabricated through this method, whereas a larger panel CPB01 was also

Fig.1: Single hat panel: shape and dimensions

Fig. 2: Three hat panel: shape and dimensions

fabricated through an established PEEK film with autoclave technique for comparison. Stacking sequences were $(45/-45/-45/45/0/90)_{sym}$:12 plies and $(45/-45/-45/45/0/90)_{sym}$:18 plies for skin and stiffener, respectively, regardless of panel sizes. Aluminum end platens were adhered with a epoxy potting agent for compression tests for both loading edges of the panel.

OUTLINE OF IMPACT TESTS AND FORMED DELAMINATION

All the panels were subjected to drop weight impact tests on a skin-stiffener bonding region with the following normalized energy levels (Unit: J/mm) by thickness at a impact point: CPA03= 2, CPA04= 4, CPB01=6.7 (with Autoclave) , CPB02=6.7 (with PEI film). These levels were determined so as to create barely visible indentation according to the previous results [3,4] and preliminary impacts. The reason why the larger panel required greater energy is supposed that some amount of impact energy was consumed in elastic deformation under a longer supporting span. Impact points were located on a mid-line parallel to the loading ends. The panels were supported on a very stiff steel table and hold by C-cramps at impact as shown in a photo of Fig. 3.

The panels were C-scanned after impact and projection area of delamination was measured by a ultrasonic C-scanner. A typical delamination image taken through a C-scanner, SDS 3300 by Krautkraemer Japan Co., is shown in Fig. 4 for CPA04 panel. It can be seen that delamination occurred almost along fusion bonding interface in this case.

Fig. 3: Photo of impact test by drop weight impactor

Fig.4: Delamination image for CPA04

Although an indication is omitted here, delamination also took place within skin and stiffener in cases of CPB01 and 02, which is similar to one shot thick plate cases [2]. Relationships between normalized impact energy and the delamination area in projection are indicated in Fig. 5 with the previous T-stiffened panel results [3,4]. A general tendency of the present impact results seems to be reasonable, although larger panels show smaller areas due to the

above reason. It can be understood that the present fusion bonding technique without autoclave worked out well from a standpoint of impact delamination.

OUTLINE OF COMPRESSION TESTS AFTER IMPACT AND DISCUSSIONS

Compression tests were conducted after 12 strain gages were glued onto the smaller panels. For the larger panes, 88 strain gages were used whereas a description of results is omitted in this paper because tests are undergoing now. For the smaller panel, a strain gage map is shown in Fig.6 where even number gages were glued back to back of odd ones on a stiffener side with some exceptions. A gage #3 was placed on an impact indentation. A number of gages, 12, was limited by 16 channel capacity of a data logger, . Thus, these strains, a load and 3 points of deflections were recorded into this data-logger, DAA 100A by Kyowa Co. JAPAN. Loading edge conditions were close to clamped due to aluminum end platens. Stainless steel tubes with sharpened slits acting as knife edges were installed along both side edges so that simply supported conditions were approximately realized. Compression load was introduced by Instron 1128 screw driven machine directly through a glued platen. A photo taken during a compression test is shown in Fig.7.

Fig.5: Relationships between normalized impact energy and delamination area

Fig. 6: Strain gage map for CPA panel

Fig. 7: Photo of compression test for CPA

Fig. 8: Stress-strain behavior for panel CPA04 (4J/mm)

Fig. 9: Stress-strain behavior for panel CPA03 (2J/mm)

Stress-strain behavior for the case where impact delamination affects the final strength, CPA04 with 4 J/mm, is shown in Fig.8. Note that delamination of this panel was already shown in Fig. 4. In Fig.8, a back-to-back pair of strain gages, #3 and #4 on the delamination, clearly indicates the behavior of delamination buckling far prior to the final failure. Such behavior is basically similar to that of a CF/PEEK T-stiffened panel in Ref. 4. It should be noted that an inflection point of stress-average strain curve for this pair provides an experimental initial buckling stress, being determined as 185MPa for CPA04. A comparison of this value with a numerically predicted initial buckling stress will be discussed later.

For CPA03 panel with 2J/mm impact, a delamination area measured by C-scan was 1/50of CPA04. Therefore, its stress-strain behavior shown in Fig. 9 does not indicate any symptom of delamination buckling before the final failure. All curves are almost straight up to the failure and coincide with each other.

Fig. 10: CAI strengths vs. impact energy

CAI strengths of the smaller hat stiffened panels without autoclave fabrication are shown in Fig.10 with comparison data of CF/PEEK panels stiffened by four T-shaped stiffeners and fabricated by autoclave technology in FY 1988 and 1989 [3,4]. Although single stiffener panels exhibit a disadvantage in terms of CAI strength comparing with multi-stiffener panels [4], the present hat-stiffened panels show excellent CAI strengths. If we take a note for 4

J/mm data of 344MPa, the present fusion bonding quality without autoclave can be regarded as excellent.

Fig. 11: Final Failure Mode of CPA 04 panel fabricated without autoclave and impacted with 4J/mm

Fig. 12: Final Failure Mode of CPA 03 panel fabricated without autoclave and impacted with 2J/mm

The reason why even a strength at 2 J/mm (CPA03) exceeds no impact strength of 4-T panel can be ascribed to a good anti-buckling property of hat stiffeners and a small delamination area by virtue of an excellent fusion bonding quality without autoclave.

Final failure modes of these panels are indicated in photos of Fig.11 and 12 taken from the stiffener side for panels CPA04 and 03, respectively. In Fig.11 with larger delamination area, a transverse failure band formation to the introduced loads can be observed which was observed in flat plate CAI tests [7] without any exception. Although this failure band formation can be well correlated experimentally with the transverse delamination penetration in the case of flat plates, ambiguous mechanism remains unexplained in the detail in the present stiffened panels. At least, the delamination buckling behavior must be a trigger of the final failure in the present case. In Fig.12 with a very small size of delamination, the final failure occurred along the loading end platen and it was not influenced by delamination. This finding is in accordance with the stress-strain behavior indicated in Fig.9. Therefore, this CAI value of 426 MPa is estimated to be close to the compression strength of the present panel without delamination. A failure mode similarity to the NASA or SACMA plates with small delamination radius was verified in Fig.12.

CAI results for three stiffener panels are being obtained now and they would be demonstrated at the presentation. Thus, a description in the current text is skipped.

PREDICTION OF BUCKLING BEHAVIOR BY FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Numerical analysis by a finite element method was conducted with simplified delamination location between skin and stiffener. A commercially supplied code, NISA-II, capable of handling laminate elements was used here. The used elements were 4 or 8 nodes isoparametric shell elements composed of assigned stacking sequence of unidirectional plies.

Outside of delaminated regions, skin-stiffener attachment flange was merely modeled as a thicker plate with total number of plies of both constituents where the thickness of fusion bonding film was neglected. This treatment implies that a slight local bending-stretching coupling may exist according to an unsymmetrical stacking sequence. In order to idealize a delaminated panel, a single delamination was assumed to exist between a skin and a hat stiffener. A projection shape of delamination was simplified into a rectangle nevertheless the true shape was the one as shown in Fig. 4. An important point of difference from the reality may be the following: Delamination edges along the fusion bonded region were considered to be free against opening deflection whereas narrow but tight bonded area remained along these edges according to a C-scan image. Boundary conditions along the loaded and the side edges were assumed to be fixed and simply supported, respectively, under consideration of potting material as discussed in Ref. 3 and tubular knife edges. Buckling under flat compression loading was simulated in the following manner. A static analysis was done first under the same specified end shortening at all the nodes along the loading edge and reaction forces at these nodes were obtained. Linear buckling analysis was done next using corresponding nodal forces along the loading line.

The employed elastic moduli for unidirectional CF/PEEK lamina are as follows: $E_L = 117.3$ GPa, $E_T = 10.3$ GPa, $G_{LT} = 4.62$ GPa, $\nu_L = 0.38$, and $\nu_{TT} = 0.5$ which are compatible with the experimental values adopted in Ref. 3. Ply thickness values for skin and stiffener regions were determined as 0.125mm and 0.13mm, respectively, from each measured thickness divided by ply number. An example of a numerical deformation pattern in the buckled state is shown in Fig.13 where absolute value of deflection has no meaning according to the nature of the eigenvalue problem. Because the delaminated area are assumed to be a rectangle as stated above, skin deformation pattern looks more square than reality. Initial buckling stress of 201 MPa was obtained and plotted by a symbol of < in Fig.8, whereas experimental buckling stress of 185 MPa determined through back-to-back strain gages was also plotted by — on the left axis in Fig.8. Note that stresses are merely plotted on the vertical axis. A correlation between these predicted and experimental buckling stress is shown to be very favorable. However, because the shape and area of the delaminated region, and geometrical structure of delamination were simplified very much in a finite element modeling, this good agreement is not considered to be a perfect description of this sort of complicated problem but some coincidence makes the agreement favorable. A discussion about this point may be summarized conservatively as follows: The present modeling of delaminated stiffened structure can predict a trend in deformation pattern of initial buckling and an approximate value of its initial buckling stress.

Fig. 13: Deformation Pattern in a Buckled Single Hat Panel under Flat Compression

CURRENT CONCLUSIONS

A fabrication technology of stiffened panels using secondary fusion bonding without autoclave was pursued with a considerable success. Two key factors in the technology consist of a development of a mold with embedded heaters and adaptation of fusion bonding film to a thermoplastic composite substrate. A goal of this technology is to realize an affordable CF/thermoplastic structure for future civil transport aircraft. A stiffener shape of a hat was chosen so as to optimize buckling load and compatibility for fusion bonding. Single and three hat stiffener panels were fabricated of CF/PEEK (AS4/APC-2) material system. Both panels exhibited similar or superior delamination resistance under impact loading to panels of CF/PEEK containing four T-stiffeners which were fabricated and tested previously. CAI strengths of the present single stiffener panels are greater than those obtained for the 4-T panels. Thus, the present fusion bonding technology is proven as a potential fabrication method for an affordable thermoplastic composite component. Some part of the reason why the present no impact strength is higher than that of the 4-T panels can be attributed to a better buckling resistance of hat stiffeners than T's. Numerical predictions by finite element analysis were conducted for a simplified mechanical model of a delaminated panel. In terms of an initial buckling stress, correlation between the predicted and experimental values was favorable. Further effort will be required for complete prediction of the behavior in the postbuckling region.

Because a baseline technology for low cost thermoplastic composite structures is established, NAL of JAPAN is seeking to find an application route of heat-resistant thermoplastic composites to future high speed commercial transport where weight reduction is a crucial technological barrier. A candidate resin there is not PEEK but PIXA, semi-crystalline polymer by Mitsui-Toatsu Co. JAPAN. Fortunately, the present fusion bonding technology for CF/PEEK can be directly transferred to CF/PIXA material system. Structural test results for this new system will be presented in the future.

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